

One of The Most Widely Used LT Method: Communicative Language Teaching.

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Abstract

There are many language teaching methods which are widely used. They appoint the way how students learn a language and impact teaching and learning process. In the article below history, components, principles of Communicative Language Teaching method is provided

Key words: *History of Communicative Language Teaching, Components of Communicative Competence, Grammatical Competence, Sociolinguistic Competence, Discourse Competence, Strategic Competence, Principles of Communicative Language Teaching*

At present language teaching is playing essential role in educational field due to the fact that the number of students wishing to learn a language or study abroad is quite high and this factor is impacting on the usage of different methods in LT among the teachers as the demand is various by the learners. Indeed, there are multiple of methods which can be used depending on the need by the learners, however, we think that CLT is one of the most popular among them. In our article below we are planning to write about Communicative Language Teaching, its history and principles which will possibly draw our readers' attention due to the fact that this teaching method is commonly utilized by the EFL and ESL teachers throughout the world.

The History of Communicative Language Teaching

If we return back to the history of communicative language teaching we find that it started developing in Great Britain in 1960s as an alternative method to the earlier structural methods when applied linguistics began to question the assumption under laying the situational language teaching and it was partly in response to Chomsky's (1965) criticism of structural theories and British functional linguists such as Firth and Holliday, as well as American sociolinguists such as Hymes, Labrov.

Actually; communicative language teaching mainly has been influenced by the American sociolinguists Hymes. He introduced the term communicative competence which was based on the two Chomsky's notions competence and performance. According to Brown, competence is "a non-observable ability to do something, to perform something". Moreover; Widdowson defines competence as knowledge of how to recognize and to use sentences for the performance of communicative acts.

What Is Communicative Competence As it mentioned before, Dell Hymes introduced "communicative competence" on the basis of Chomsky's notions competence and performance, He believed that second language acquisition, to acquire a language, learners should go beyond the language rules, but also how to communicate using those rules, he stated that "communicative competence is the aspect of our competence that enables us to convey and interpret messages and negotiate meanings interpersonally within specific contexts"

Hymes stated that the speaker needs to communicate the language and to be able to use it according to the socio-cultural environment. This means that the speaker of foreign language should use the language in a specific context. This idea interpreted by Bachman into communicative language

ability. Canale, Swain and Savignon conceived communicative competence in terms of four components: grammatical competence, discourse competence, socio-cultural competence, and strategic competence.

Components of Communicative Competence

Grammatical Competence: Brown states that the grammatical competence “encompasses knowledge of lexical items and rules of morphology, syntax, sentence grammar, semantics and phonology”. In other words; the ability of students’ to produce accurately structured comprehensible utterances.

Sociolinguistic Competence: it helps the speakers to be “contextually appropriately”. This means to use socio cultural messages in meaningful ways.

Discourse Competence: According to Brown discourses competence “the ability to connect sentences ...and to form meaningful whole out of a series utterances” In other words; the speaker’s ability to shape and communicate purposely using cohesion and coherence.

Strategic Competence: for Canale and Swain strategic competence it is “how to cope in an authentic communicative situation and how to keep the communicative channel open” in other words, the learners’ ability to enhance the effectiveness of communication. 14

Principles of Communicative Language Teaching. The main characteristics of communicative language teaching are identified by Brown as:

1. Classroom goals are focused on all of the components (grammatical, discourse, functional, sociolinguistic, and strategy) .of communicative competence; In other words; students should not only learn the grammatical rules and memorize vocabulary but also know how to use them in a given situation.
2. Language techniques are designed to engage learners in the pragmatic, authentic, functional use of language for meaningful purposes, organizational language forms are not the central focus but rather aspects of language that enable the learner meaningfully engaged in language use. In other words, different activities or tasks which are used in the classrooms are addressed to help students to use the language for meaningful purposes.
3. Fluency and accuracy are seen as complementary principles underlying communicative techniques. At times fluency may have to take on more important than accuracy in order to keep learners meaningfully engaged in language use. In other words; teachers focus more on fluency since the primary goal of CLT is getting students to communicate meaningfully
4. Students in a communicative class ultimately have to use the language productively and receptively in unrehearsed contexts outside the classroom; classroom tasks must therefore equip students with the skill necessary for communication those contexts. In other words students must be provided with the important skills needed to communicate in real world context
5. Students are given opportunities to focus on their own learning process through an understanding of their awn styles of learning and through the development of appropriate strategies for autonomous learning.
6. The role of the teacher is that of a facilitator and a guide

These characteristics show the main focus of communicative language teaching. To sum up, CLT enables students to communicate in the foreign language using the different types of communicative competence. However, the language techniques encourage them to use the target language in different situations. In addition; communicative language teaching pays less attention to accuracy the degree to which learners use target language is remarkably free of errors, students errors are tolerated into some extent since it focuses more on meaning and fluency which helps students to communicate

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

spontaneously, the teacher in CLT approach is a facilitator not a controller. Besides that, Communicative approach came into existence as a solution to many of Language Teaching issues. It helped to learn a language through interactive and interesting activities, techniques which made the class more fun and pleasant. These factors were actually resolution to avoid using distinct methods which sometimes accepted as a less interesting by learners in LT which many teachers had challenges by having limited opportunities in their classes.

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